

Estimating underwater light attenuation from space – A spectral approach for case 2 marine waters

Andreas Holbach^{*}, Sanjina Upadhyay Stæhr, Peter Anton Upadhyay Stæhr, Stiig Markager

Institute of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

HIGHLIGHTS

- Novel spectral model estimates spectrally resolved underwater light attenuation.
- Sentinel-3 IOPs enable large-scale K_d^{PAR} monitoring with high spatial coverage.
- Strong agreement with *in situ* K_d^{PAR} data ($n = 1458$, $R = 0.63$).
- Improved accuracy over simpler satellite-based K_d estimates.
- Supports EU directives with enhanced environmental status assessments.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Jay Gan

Keywords:

Diffuse light attenuation coefficient
Water clarity
Spectral model
Ocean optics
Coastal waters
Sentinel-3
Monitoring

ABSTRACT

Water clarity is a key indicator of marine ecosystem health, responding to eutrophication and influencing the distribution of phototrophic life on the seafloor. Traditional ship-based measurements of underwater light profiles and diffuse light attenuation coefficients (K_d) remain fundamental for environmental monitoring, including in Danish waters. However, satellite-based estimates of water clarity are often challenged by optically complex (case 2) waters and limited spectral coverage.

This study presents a novel empirical spectral modelling approach across the range of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) from 400 to 700 nm that

- integrates existing individual spectral models of inherent optical properties (IOPs),
- applies Sentinel-3 satellite-derived IOPs at 443 nm in this model,
- employs a multivariate outlier removal procedure to enhance accuracy, and
- estimates K_d^{PAR} through an iterative procedure mimicking the way it usually is determined *in situ* with PAR sensors.

Model-derived K_d^{PAR} estimates were validated against *in situ* measurements from Danish marine waters (2018–2023) and compared with two simpler non-spectral satellite-based approaches.

Results showed strong agreement between modelled and *in situ* K_d^{PAR} ($n = 1458$, $R = 0.63$), outperforming existing satellite-based methods. The new K_d^{PAR} product effectively captured spatial and temporal variability in

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: anho@ecos.au.dk (A. Holbach).

complex case 2 waters, though discrepancies were noted in optically shallow areas, heterogeneous water columns, and seasonal phytoplankton shifts.

These findings highlight the potential of operational satellite-derived IOP products as a robust proxy for water clarity, providing a valuable supplement to limited *in situ* data. The improved spatial and temporal coverage supports enhanced environmental monitoring, aligning with EU Water Framework and Marine Strategy Framework Directives.

1. Introduction

The composition and functioning of marine ecosystems and habitats are strongly dependent not just on the availability of light, but also the spectral composition of light penetrating the water column and reaching the sea floor (Markager and Sand-Jensen, 1992; Kirk, 1994). Light availability is the primary driver of photosynthesis and growth of phytoplankton and aquatic macrophyte vegetation, providing energy for all trophic levels in marine ecosystems (Kirk, 1994; Wetzel, 2001). In particular, the spectral distribution and intensity of light in the wavelength range 400–700 nm, called photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), is crucial for the photosynthesis of underwater primary producers (Kirk, 1994). In aquatic ecosystems, the amount of light available at different depths, such as for underwater vegetation, depends on its propagation through the water column, which is regulated by water clarity. Water clarity, a fundamental characteristic of aquatic ecosystems, is determined by the distinct absorption and scattering properties of optically active substances in water (Kirk, 1994). This is quantified by the wavelength (λ) dependent diffuse light attenuation coefficient K_d^λ (m^{-1}), which describes the exponential decay of light as it travels through the water column (Kirk, 1984; Gordon, 1989).

In addition to water itself, three main groups of substances contribute to light attenuation in the water column: 1) phytoplankton pigments, 2) colored organic matter (CDOM and detritus), and 3) suspended particles that cause scattering. The absorption and scattering properties of these substances, which shape the underwater light field, are referred to as Inherent Optical Properties (IOPs) (Kirk, 1984). Unlike the apparent optical property (AOP) K_d^λ , IOPs cannot be directly determined.

In practice and operational monitoring, water clarity or light attenuation are typically not measured as the spectrally resolved K_d^λ , but instead as a generalized average diffuse light attenuation coefficient K_d^{PAR} , or the simpler but still useful Secchi depth, which both integrate across the entire PAR range (Markager and Fossing, 2014). For a homogeneously mixed water column, K_d^λ can be assumed to be constant with depth. For a single wavelength, the light attenuation with increasing depth can then be described by Beer-Lambert's law as $I_z = I_0^{-K_d^\lambda z}$. However, as K_d^λ is not constant across the PAR spectrum, the spectral composition of downwelling light will change throughout the water column. In fact, the fraction of light at wavelengths with low K_d^λ values will increase with depth, which theoretically would lead to a systematic decrease of overall K_d^{PAR} with depth. *In situ*, this effect may be counteracted by increased effects of scattering with depth (Kirk, 1994), hidden behind noise in PAR-profile data, and/or overruled by inhomogeneous IOP distributions through the water column, e.g. related to plankton accumulation in certain depths, or particle resuspension near the sediment surface. Nevertheless, it is generally assumed that IOPs are evenly distributed throughout the water column and that PAR follows an exponential decay function with increasing depth (Markager and Fossing, 2014).

In the Danish national monitoring program (NOVANA) and in many other parts of the world (Markager and Fossing, 2014; Lee et al., 2018; Kratzer et al., 2019), water clarity is typically measured at defined stations using a Secchi disk or with *in situ* underwater PAR sensors. While this results in robust detailed datasets for long-term assessments at particular points in space, these tend to be highly limited in terms of

spatial and temporal coverage due to associated financial and logistical challenges with ship-based monitoring (Luis et al., 2019; Kratzer et al., 2019). Moreover for practical and economic reasons, these measurements are generally made at deeper and central locations away from the shallow productive coastal zone (Kratzer et al., 2019). However, water clarity in the coastal sublittoral zone is very sensitive to a range of human activities, both in the surrounding catchments and directly in the coastal zone (Kratzer and Allart, 2023). Eutrophication driven by enrichment with land derived nutrients stimulates phytoplankton growth and biomass. This, in turn, reduces light penetration through the water column by increasing light attenuation from both biomass and organic matter (Kratzer et al., 2019). Although *in situ* monitoring of K_d^{PAR} in the Danish seas is intense with biweekly to monthly samples of >200 stations, the extensive coastline covering >7300 km, and 105.000 km² of sea (Exclusive Economic Zone; EEZ) makes it challenging to provide representative monitoring of all coastal waterbodies at relevant time scales.

In comparison, satellite-based ocean observations provide almost global and daily coverage with spectral imagery at different levels of spatial and temporal resolution, bearing huge potential to supplement the spatially and temporally limited local ship-based *in situ* measurements (Stæhr et al., 2023). Successful use of such observations could provide a cost-effective way to monitor optical water quality parameters across all marine water bodies. Spectral reflectance data from the satellite sensor 'Ocean and Land Color Instrument' (OLCI) on board the Sentinel-3 satellites, are processed operationally to obtain level 2 products with estimates of three IOPs in the water column for each recorded image. This is done through coupling 'Alternative Atmospheric Correction' (AAC) and the 'Case-2 Regional Coast Color' (C2RCC) processor (Doerffer, 2010; Brockmann et al., 2016). All the resulting data are made publicly available at several platforms, such as EUMETSAT & Copernicus. In this study, Sentinel-3 OLCI level 2 products are referred to as 'S3OL2'.

The IOPs output by C2RCC contain pigment absorption coefficient (a_{pig}), absorption coefficient of detritus and gelbstoff (a_{dg}) and total scattering coefficient (b_{tot}), each at 443 nm wavelength. However, as highlighted earlier, light attenuation is a spectral function of wavelength, and each optically active component has its own spectral light attenuation pattern, which can vary geographically, with depth and in time, particularly in coastal waters (Kirk, 1977; Loisel et al., 2014). Phytoplankton composition, ecological state and physiology (Stæhr and Markager, 2004; Stæhr et al., 2004), as well as specific sources and fates of organic and/or suspended matter affecting CDOM (Stedmon et al., 2000) and detritus (Obrador and Pretus, 2008) are among the main drivers of this variation. As a result, variations in spectral K_d^λ influence the spectral composition of light throughout the water column, ultimately affecting the overall K_d^{PAR} .

The importance of estimating spectral K_d^λ has been emphasized in various studies, including those on heat transfer in the upper ocean (Zaneveld et al., 1981; Morel and Antoine, 1994), photosynthesis and other biological processes in the water column (Platt et al., 1988; Sathyendranath et al., 1989; Saulquin et al., 2013), and turbidity (Turb) in oceanic and coastal waters (Jerlov, 1976). By combining high-resolution spatial and temporal IOP data from Sentinel-3 with empirical spectral *in situ* IOP models (Stedmon et al., 2000; Stæhr and Markager, 2004), it is possible to estimate K_d^λ (m^{-1}) throughout the PAR

spectrum. From this, the overall K_d^{PAR} (m^{-1}) can be estimated at high spatial and temporal resolution in marine waters.

In this context, we present a novel empirical spectral modelling approach across PAR that

- integrates existing individual spectral models of IOPs,
- applies Sentinel-3 satellite-derived IOPs at 443 nm in this model,
- employs a multivariate outlier removal procedure to enhance accuracy, and
- estimates K_d^{PAR} through an iterative procedure mimicking the way it usually is determined *in situ* with PAR sensors.

Using matchup analysis with *in situ*-based K_d^{PAR} measurements from the NOVANA program, we compare the performance of this new spectral-based K_d^{PAR} estimate with other non-spectral estimates derived from S3OL2 products. Our analysis covers monitoring stations across the entire Danish Seas over the period from 2018 to 2023.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area, spatial working grid and geographic data

The study area (Fig. 1) covers the Danish Seas including parts of the North Sea, Skagerrak, Kattegat, Danish Straits and the western Baltic Sea. This study area is characterized by pronounced environmental gradients from the saline open North Sea to the low saline Baltic Sea (Staeher et al., 2023). Shallow waters, numerous narrow straits, estuaries, and sounds, and coastal eutrophication further characterize these waters. These conditions lead to optically very complex waters, where the light environment is determined by all major optically active components (1. algal biomass, 2. CDOM, 3. detritus, and 4. suspended particles).

2.2. Spatial working grid

We generated a spatial working grid covering the geographical bounding box between 3 and 17°E and 54–59°N for the study area. The grid has 880 rows and 1680 columns, a spatial resolution of 500×500

m, and a spatial extent between 140,000–980,000 m Easting and 6,020,000–6,460,000 m Northing in the epsg:3044 coordinate reference system (ETRS89/UTM zone 32 N (N-E) - EPSG:3044). This grid was used as basis for all spatial analyses carried out in this study.

2.3. Bathymetry and coastline

Two available bathymetry datasets were merged: the official Danish bathymetry model with 50×50 m resolution (Geodatastyrelsen, 2024) and bathymetry from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet, 2024) with approximately 116×116 m resolution. The Danish dataset covers only areas within the Danish EEZ. Both datasets were spatially projected on the spatial working grid by calculating average values for each 500×500 m pixel. While merging, priority was given to the higher resolution Danish dataset. Negative bathymetry values (tidal areas above the mean sea level) were replaced by zeros. Further, for a detailed description of coastline features, we used the official Danish land polygon dataset (Klimadatasyrelsen, 2025). Pixels of the working grid, overlapping by $>50\%$ with the land polygon, were classified as land and not further considered for the marine analyses performed in this study.

2.4. *In situ* PAR and K_d^{PAR} monitoring data

In this study, PAR is treated as photon flux density PFD ($\text{mol} \times \text{m}^{-2} \times \text{s}^{-1}$). As part of the operational national environmental monitoring program of Denmark (NOVANA), K_d^{PAR} values are monitored and typically derived from PAR depth-profiles (Markager and Fossing, 2014). PAR at depth z (I_z), relative to surface PAR (I_0), is ln-transformed and plotted *versus* depth z . Assuming an exponential decay of light with increasing depth, K_d^{PAR} can be derived through linear regression from –

$$\ln\left(\frac{I_z}{I_0}\right) = K_d^{PAR} \times z + c$$
 (Markager and Fossing, 2014). Near-surface and deep PAR measurements are subject to noise and therefore manually excluded from the individual depth-profiles, the NOVANA technical guidelines recommend the use of PAR profiles from the near surface down to either just above the seabed or to a depth where PAR decreased

Fig. 1. Study area, bathymetry and 207 *in situ* monitoring stations (denoted by orange circles) for diffuse light attenuation coefficient K_d^{PAR} across the Danish Seas. Highlighted letters indicate the following marine regions used for reference in the text: a: North Sea, b: Skagerrak, c: Limfjord, d: Kattegat, e: Little Belt, f: Great Belt, g: The Sound, h: South Funen Archipelago, i: Arkona Basin.

to ca. 1 % of its surface intensity (Markager and Fossing, 2014).

Data from *in situ* measurements are collected and stored in the Danish surface water database (overfladevandsdatabasen, ODA), which is publicly available (<https://odaforalle.au.dk/>). From this database, we acquired all data on marine K_d^{PAR} values for the years 2018–2023. In total, 13,318 K_d^{PAR} values from 218 monitoring stations were received. K_d^{PAR} values were aggregated as daily averages per station, and we only kept values coinciding with valid bathymetry for the corresponding pixel of the working grid. This left 12,596 K_d^{PAR} values from 207 monitoring stations (Fig. 1).

2.5. Sentinel-3 OLCI level 2 water full-resolution products

The two Sentinel-3 satellites (A & B) are equipped with OLCI, a spectral sensor acquiring images across 21 spectral bands at a spatial resolution of approximately 300×300 m at sea level. For marine areas, the raw images are processed by the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) and made available at different processing levels.

At level 2, two sets of products are made available: One based on ‘baseline atmospheric correction’ (BAC), and another one based on AAC. BAC products were designed for ‘Open Waters, with a spectral signature dominated by phytoplankton pigments’ (EUMETSAT, 2024). A relevant variable from the S3OL2-BAC products for this study is K_d^{490} , which we use for comparisons in the Results section.

AAC products, in contrast, are coupled with C2RCC, which is a neural-network algorithm developed for optically complex waters affected by several optically active compounds. C2RCC operationally delivers S3OL2 products with estimates of IOPs and derived concentrations of optically active compounds in the surface water. The main output of C2RCC is three IOPs: 1) pigment absorption coefficient (a_{pig}), 2) integrated absorption coefficient of detritus and gelbstoff (a_{dg}), and 3) total scattering coefficient (b_{tot}) at 443 nm wavelength. In S3OL2 products, these are made available to the public after conversion to more understandable concentration units using empirical default scaling factors, which can be variable. Both BAC and AAC products are further based on two assumptions: 1) an infinitely deep and 2) homogeneously mixed water column (Doerffer, 2010).

2.5.1. Product selection

We acquired the highest quality level of the available products at the time of data access (14.06.2024). Hence, we acquired all reprocessed (01.01.2018–28.04.2021) and non-time-critical (29.04.2021–31.12.2023) S3OL2 products intersecting with a rectangular geographical bounding box between 3° and 17° E and 54° – 59° N for the years 2018 till 2023. This bounding box covers the entire Danish EEZ and our defined working grid. For this task, we used the EUMETSAT Data Access Client (eumdac, link), an open access python library. In total, 6372 S3OL2 products were downloaded for further processing.

2.5.2. Data processing

All data handling was performed in R (v. R-4.2.1), and all spatial data processing was done with the R-library ‘terra’ (v. 1.8–15). For each image, we loaded the variables KD490_M07 and KD490_M07_err from the S3OL2-BAC products, as well as CHL_NN, CHL_NN_err, ADG443_NN, TSM_NN from the S3OL2-AAC products from the respective NetCDF files. To limit the amount of uncertainty in the following analyses, we only considered datasets where the originally estimated K_d^{490} was larger than the respective uncertainty estimate ($KD490_M07 > KD490_M07_err$), and likewise where the estimated chlorophyll concentration was larger than the respective uncertainty estimate ($CHL_NN > CHL_NN_err$). Further, we applied the following water quality and science flags from the WQSF variable to mask out datasets with likely false or highly uncertain estimates: ‘INVALID’, ‘CLOUD’, ‘SNOW_ICE’, ‘SUSPECT’, ‘HISOLZEN’, ‘SATURATED’, ‘HIGHGLINT’,

‘CLOUD_AMBIGUOUS’, ‘CLOUD_MARGIN’, ‘OCNN_FAIL’. We did not apply the ‘INLAND_WATER’ flag, as several inner Danish water bodies such as the Limfjord would otherwise be cut out from the images. All remaining datasets from a single image were with corresponding longitudes and latitudes transformed into a spatial point vector, which was reprojected and rasterized onto the 500×500 m working grid. Each pixel received daily mean values of log-transformed data. We used log-transformed data to minimize impact of single outlying data values from individual pixels of the original satellite images. Each variable from each S3OL2 product was saved as individual GeoTIFF file. In a second step and for each variable, we averaged all images from the same day into one.

2.5.3. Multivariate outlier removal

S3OL2 C2RCC products come with 3 IOP based variables CHL_NN, ADG443_NN, and TSM_NN. In nature, these three variables are considerably correlated, and for training of the neural network at the heart of C2RCC, unrealistic spectra/combinations have been omitted (Doerffer, 2010). In S3OL2 products, however, unrealistic combinations of the three variables can occur, even after flagging with the described WQSF. Hence, we implemented a multivariate identification method for potentially outlying datapoints based on Section 6.2 in ISO (2010). We used the minimum covariance determinant (MCD) estimator for robust estimates of the means of and the covariance matrix between the three variables on log-scale. As a data subset, we extracted all the daily aggregated variable sets from all 207 NOVANA stations (Fig. 1). In total, 71,516 sets were extracted, and we assumed a fraction of 95 % of ‘good’ data sets to base the MCD estimation on (ISO, 2010). All sets with corresponding Mahalanobis distance >97.5 percentile of a chi-squared distribution with 3 degrees of freedom were then classified as potential outliers.

2.5.4. Spectral modelling of light attenuation

Throughout this study we used a spectral resolution of 1 nm. All the steps of data processing from the daily aggregated S3OL2 products are schematically visualized in Fig. 2. Further, one specific example from station 93,110,002 on 1st march 2023 is visualized spectrally in Fig. 3, and other selected examples are shown in suppl. Figs. S4–14.

2.5.5. Spectral IOP estimation

2.5.5.1. Spectral pigment absorption. The variable CHL_{NN} in S3OL2 C2RCC products include chlorophyll concentrations Chl ($\mu g \times L^{-1}$) (Fig. 2). This concentration value is based on an estimate for the pigment absorption at 443 nm a_{pig}^{443} (m^{-1}) according to the following equation (Doerffer, 2010):

$$hl = a_{pig}^{443, Chl_{exp}} \times Chl_{fact} \quad (1)$$

The two ‘so-called’ scaling factors get assigned the following empirical default values: $Chl_{exp} = 1.04$ and $Chl_{fact} = 21.0$. However, these factors can be regionally variable (Brockmann et al., 2016). To derive the original a_{pig}^{443} , Eq. (1) is rearranged into:

$$a_{pig}^{443} = \left(\frac{Chl}{Chl_{fact}} \right)^{Chl_{exp}^{-1}} \quad (2)$$

Stæhr and Markager (2004) have shown that the Chl-specific light attenuation coefficient a_{chl}^{λ} is decreasing with increasing Chl. They developed an empirical spectral linear regression model with 4 nm resolution, to describe for each wavelength the concentration dependence of a_{chl}^{λ} :

$$\ln(a_{chl}^{\lambda}) = -B^{\lambda} \times \ln(Chl) + \ln(A^{\lambda}) \quad (3)$$

Here, A^{λ} and B^{λ} are coefficients for the spectral linear regressions (Table 3 in Stæhr and Markager (2004)). As $a_{chl}^{\lambda} = \frac{a_{chl}}{Chl}$, we can use this

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of data flow from three C2RCC complex water products to the final estimate of diffuse light attenuation coefficient for photosynthetically active radiation K_d^{PAR} . (1) Ståhr and Markager (2004); (2) Original data from the project “Danish Environmental monitoring of COastal waters – DECO”; (3) Stedmon et al. (2000); (4) Doerffer (2010); (5) Woźniak et al. (2018); (6) Zhang et al. (2010); (7) Lee et al. (2005); (8) Hedley and Mobley (2019); (9) Mobley (1994).

relationship to derive the spectral pigment absorption at any hypothetical concentration of Chl:

$$a_{chl}(\lambda) = \frac{a_{chl}^*(\lambda)}{Chl} \tag{4}$$

Hence, we can use the estimated a_{pig}^{443} from S3OL2 products to estimate the corresponding spectral a_{pig}^λ across PAR from 400 to 700 nm (see green point and line in the example in Fig. 3). The spectral resolution of Ståhr and Markager (2004) model was refined to 1 nm by linear interpolation.

2.5.5.2. Spectral CDOM and detritus absorption. The ADG_{NN}^{443} variable in S3OL2 C2RCC products contains estimates of the aggregated absorption

coefficient of CDOM and detritus at 443 nm a_{dg}^{443} (Fig. 3). This IOP was first split into estimates of CDOM specific a_g^{443} and detritus specific absorption a_d^{443} using an empirical constant ratio based on 58 reference spectra from the study area (suppl. Fig. S1; background dataset of and Stedmon et al. (2000): $a_g^{443} = 0.7 \times a_{dg}^{443}$, $a_d^{443} = 0.3 \times a_{dg}^{443}$. This constant distribution ratio had Pearson correlations of $R = 0.95$ and $R = 0.75$, respectively. Spectral a_g^λ and a_d^λ was then estimated using the following empirical spectral model described in e.g. Stedmon et al. (2000) and Doerffer (2010):

$$a_{d/g}^\lambda = a_{d/g}^{443} \times e^{-S_{d/g} \times (\lambda - 443)} \tag{5}$$

S is an exponential slope coefficient and is defined differently for

Fig. 3. Spectral contributions from different optically active components to the overall modelled spectral K_d^λ (example of NOVANA station 93,110,002 on 01.03.2023). The colored circles represent the IOPs directly derived from S3OL2 products. The corresponding-colored lines represent the applied spectral models for each of the IOPs. The dashed and dotted lines represent absorption and backscattering coefficients of pure sea water. Finally, the red line is the derived overall spectral K_d^λ .

CDOM and detritus. Stedmon et al. (2000) described S_g as a salinity and location dependent parameter: In open water, S_g can be approximated by a linear relation with salinity Sal as $S_g = -0.006/35 \times Sal + 0.025$, while it within estuaries and fjords showed an approximately constant value of $S_g = 0.019$ (see Fig. 4 in Stedmon et al. (2000)). We used this information to develop a simple spatial model for S_g (suppl. Fig. S2). For detritus, S_d coefficient was assumed constant with a value of 0.008, as inherited from Doerffer (2010). (see yellow/orange points and lines in the example in Fig. 3).

2.5.5.3. Spectral scattering and backscattering. The TSM_{NN} variable of the S3OL2 C2RCC products contains estimates for the total suspended matter concentration (TSM) (Fig. 3). Like Chl , this product is derived from a prior estimate of the total particle scattering coefficient at 443 nm

$$(b_{tot}^{443}):$$

$$TSM = b_{tot}^{443 TSM_{exp}} \times TSM_{fact} \tag{6}$$

where $TSM_{exp} = 1.06$ and $TSM_{fact} = 0.942$ are respective empirical default scaling factors. Likewise, the IOP b_{tot}^{443} can be derived from restructuring Eq. (6) into:

$$b_{tot}^{443} = \left(\frac{TSM}{TSM_{fact}} \right)^{TSM_{exp}^{-1}} \tag{7}$$

Due to a lack of reference data from the study area, we assumed a literature based Doerffer (2010) spectral relationship for b_{tot}^λ as:

Fig. 4. Temporal distribution of frequencies of K_d^{PAR} records from both *in situ* measurements in the NOVANA programme (green) and S3OL2 C2RCC products for all analyzed 207 stations. The light-blue parts of bars for S3OL2 represent values excluded from further analysis due to either multivariate outlier detection (MVO-excl.), or due to month- and optical depth-related deviation analysis (DEV-excl.).

$$b_{tot}(\lambda) = b_{tot}^{443} \times \left(\frac{\lambda}{443} \right)^{-S_{b_{tot}}} \quad (8)$$

where we assumed the spectral slope to be constant $S_{b_{tot}} = 0.8$ (Doerffer, 2010). The relationship between particle scattering (b_p^i) and backscattering (b_b^i) coefficient is complex and dependent on the so-called particle phase functions, which describe the angular dependency of scattered light in relation to the incident light beam. An empirical ratio of $\frac{b_p^{555}}{b_b^{555}} \sim 0.01$ was derived from Fig. 4 and Table 1 in Wozniak et al. (2018) for the Baltic Sea. Further, Zhang et al. (2010) have shown that this ratio can be regarded as wavelength-independent across large parts of the PAR spectrum from 400 to 700 nm. Hence, we estimated spectral backscattering coefficients as, $b_{b_{tot}}^i = b_{tot}^i \times 0.01$. (see blue point and line in the example in Fig. 3).

2.5.6. Spectral K_d^λ modelling

An empirical model for spectral K_d estimations in the euphotic zone was derived from Eq. (11) from Lee et al. (2005):

$$K_d^\lambda = (1 + 0.005\theta_a) \times a^\lambda + 4.18 \times (1 - 0.52 \times e^{-10.8 \times a^\lambda}) \times b_b^i \quad (9)$$

where θ_a is the sun zenith angle, a^λ is the sum of all absorption coefficients, and b_b^i is the sum of all backscattering coefficients at wavelength λ . The solar zenith angle is a spatio-temporal variable. For simplicity, however, in this study we only applied an average solar zenith angle at noon time for each pixel and the period from March–October. This period is justified later in Section 3.4 based on actual data. Solar zenith angles were calculated using the R-library ‘solarPos’ (v. 1.0).

In addition to the spectral IOPs described above, the spectral absorption (a_w^i) and backscattering (b_b^i) coefficients of pure seawater also need to be taken into account (see dashed and dotted lines in the example in Fig. 3). These were derived from HydroLight — a radiative transfer numerical model that computes radiance distributions for natural water bodies (Hedley and Mobley, 2019) (Fig. 3). For the conversion of pure seawater scattering to backscattering, Mobley et al. (2004) provides a backscattering ratio of 0.058 provided in Table 3.11.

The red line in Fig. 3 represents the result of applying the spectral K_d^λ model (Eq. (8)) to all spectral IOP model products derived from a single pixel on a specific day in the S3OL2 C2RCC products.

2.5.7. K_d^{PAR} estimation

To estimate K_d^{PAR} from a spectral K_d^λ model (Fig. 3) in accordance with *in situ* monitoring (Markager and Fossing, 2014), the incoming solar PAR must be theoretically propagated through the water column until it reaches either the local maximum water depth z_{max} or a specified lower fraction of the surface light intensity. Here, it is important to handle PAR intensity as ($mol \times m^{-2} \times s^{-1}$). In this study, we tested two simplifications for PFD just below the water surface PFD_0 :

1) a constant distribution from 400 to 700 nm,

2) a site-specific average PFD_0 spectrum modelled using the ‘radtran’ function from the R-library ‘trawllight’ (v. 3.2.0).

For the latter, we used actual coordinates and average solar zenith angles for each station, assuming a constant air pressure of 1013 mbar, a precipitable water vapor of 1 cm, power of the Ångström Turb expression of 1.3, and an air mass with marine aerosols.

We propagated incoming PFD_0 through 1 m depth z intervals of the water column at spectral intervals of 1 nm. For each depth, we applied Beer-Lambert’s law as $PFD_z^\lambda = PFD_0^\lambda \times e^{-K_d^\lambda \times z}$ and tested whether $z \geq z_{max}$, or $\Sigma PFD_z \leq 0.01 \times \Sigma PFD_0$. These conditions equal those applied *in situ* for NOVANA monitoring (Markager and Fossing, 2014), and when one of these was fulfilled, we derived the corresponding overall diffuse light attenuation coefficient as:

$$K_d^{PAR} = - \frac{\ln \left(\frac{\Sigma PFD_z}{\Sigma PFD_0} \right)}{z} \quad (10)$$

3. Results

3.1. *In situ* K_d^{PAR} data from NOVANA

99 % of the 12,596 daily aggregated NOVANA K_d^{PAR} values ranged in between 0.138 and 3.57 m^{-1} . *In situ* monitoring of K_d^{PAR} focusses on summer and autumn in Danish marine waters. 67 % of all observations are made from June to November (Fig. 4).

3.2. Multivariate outlier removal on S3OL2 data

In total, 71,516 sets of the S3OL2 variables CHL_{NN} , ADG_{NN}^{443} , and TSM_{NN} were extracted from the 207 locations of NOVANA station locations. The robust MCD estimation for 95 % of the data resulted in the center and variance/covariance values provided in.

Through Mahalanobis distance, potential multivariate outliers were identified by comparing with the threshold explained in Section 2.5.3. In Fig. 5, paired scatterplots of the three S3OL2 variables are shown, differentiating statistical outliers (hollow black points) from likely valid variable sets (solid green points). Approximately 12 % of the variable sets were classified as outliers and removed from further data analysis (see also Fig. 4).

3.3. Satellite-based estimates of K_d^{PAR}

After multivariate outlier detection, we applied the full spectral IOP modelling approach, as schematically outlined in Fig. 2, to estimate K_d^{PAR} for the remaining 63,024 variable sets based on S3OL2 C2RCC products. For the assumption of a constant spectral PAR irradiation from 400 to 700 nm, 99 % of the S3OL2 K_d^{PAR} values ranged between 0.102 and 1.67 m^{-1} , while for the site-specific irradiation model, they ranged between 0.101 and 1.63 m^{-1} . Unlike *in situ* monitoring, the majority (~56 %) of S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} estimates were derived from the period March to June (Fig. 4).

3.4. Day-precise matchups: deviation and relation patterns

From the 63,024 S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} estimates extracted for all 207 NOVANA stations, we identified day-precise matchups with *in situ* K_d^{PAR} estimates in 1662 cases. These cases were used to analyze deviation and relation patterns.

It is known that low solar zenith angles typically pose challenges for ocean color data. For Danish latitudes, it has been shown that data from November to February in general is problematic (Stæhr et al., 2023). Additionally, one of the fundamental assumptions in the background of C2RCC processor is an infinitely deep water column (Doerffer, 2010), as

Table 1

Robust estimates of multivariate center and variance/covariance between the three S3OL2 variables CHL_{NN} , ADG_{NN}^{443} , and TSM_{NN} based on MCD for 95 % of the data (ISO, 2010).

S3OL2 variable	Center	Variance/Covariance		
		$\log CHL_{NN}$	$\log ADG_{NN}^{443}$	$\log TSM_{NN}$
$\log CHL_{NN}$	0.403	0.104	0.099	0.111
$\log ADG_{NN}^{443}$	-0.620		0.136	0.113
$\log TSM_{NN}$	-1.97			0.190

Fig. 5. Multivariate outlier analysis based on 71,516 sets of the S3OL2 variables CHL_{NN} , ADG_{NN}^{443} , and TSM_{NN} , extracted from the 207 NOVANA station locations (see Fig. 1). Open black points ($\sim 12\%$ of all points) are considered outliers and removed from further analysis. The green circles represent the remaining $\sim 88\%$ that were included in the analysis. Outlier detection was based on MCD estimator, providing robust estimates of the means and the covariance matrix between three variables on a log-scale. Outliers were then identified using a threshold for the Mahalanobis distance (ISO, 2010).

reflection signals from the bottom would bias the C2RCCs IOP output. The useless optical depth $\tau = K_d \times z$ reflects the potential influence of sediment reflectance on remote sensing reflectance. We used a generalized estimate of τ based on *in situ* K_d^{PAR} and bathymetry for each measurement.

Fig. 5 presents the deviation between day-precise matchups, expressed as $|\Delta \log(K_d^{PAR})|$ across months and optical depth classes. Results are shown under the assumption of constant spectral PAR irradiation, though deviations would be only marginally different for the site-specific spectral irradiation model. Deviations are generally higher in February and November compared to the months from March to October. No matchups were available from January and December. At

$\tau < 1.5$, we observed increased deviation between the two K_d^{PAR} estimation methods. As a result, we selected 1458 matchup pairs for further analysis, focusing on data from March to October and where $\tau \geq 1.5$ (see also Fig. 4 for S3OL2 data).

To depict the quality of the new spectrally modelled estimates of K_d^{PAR} , based on S3OL2 C2RCC products, we compared its performance with those of two other more simple approaches: The direct S3OL2-BAC product K_d^{490} , and a non-spectral K_d^{443} only considering S3OL2 C2RCCs direct IOP outputs for a wavelength of 443 nm (Fig. 7). The S3OL2 K_d^{PAR} are shown under the assumption of constant spectral PAR irradiation. The spectral model to estimate K_d^{PAR} clearly revealed the highest Pearson correlation coefficient of $R = 0.63$, compared to 0.46 and 0.51 for K_d^{490}

and K_d^{443} , respectively. When testing the two different approaches for spectral PAR irradiation (see Section 2.5.7), correlation was slightly higher when assuming constant spectral PAR irradiation, as opposed to a site specific modelled spectral PAR irradiance ($R = 0.6321$ vs. 0.6317), which is why we chose to continue with this approach for further analyses, also with respect to computational ease. For each graph, geometric mean linear regression models are shown for log-transformed data. Geometric mean regression assumes uncertainty in both variables, which makes sense here as both variables represent modelled approximations of K_d^{PAR} from different methodological approaches and distributions in space and time. In part (c) of Fig. 7, comparison to the 1:1 line is also shown, as the S3OL2 model is meant to estimate the same parameter as measured *in situ*. The fitted linear regression model (shown with $p = 0.95$ confidence interval) is very close to the 1:1 line and both slope and intercept are not significantly different from 1 and 0, respectively (two-sided Student's t -test, $p = 0.05$). Further we can see that exclusion of matchups from the months between November to February and with $\tau < 1.5$ removes many of the broader scattered points.

3.5. Spatial and temporal patterns of K_d^{PAR}

We assume that K_d^{PAR} in coastal and oceanic waters is influenced by

depth and proximity to the shore, where terrestrial inputs, sediment resuspension, and eutrophication can enhance light attenuation. Hence, we define 'Integrated Bathymetric Proximity' (IBP) in km^2 as the minimum spatially integrated sum of bathymetric values from oceanic points to the coast, quantifying the overall proximity of points in the ocean to the shore (suppl. Fig. S3). In Fig. 8 (a), we visualize K_d^{PAR} from both *in situ* monitoring and the spectral model based on S3OL2 across intervals of increasing IBP. We can see an overall similar spatial pattern with decreasing K_d^{PAR} distributions along increasing IBP. In Fig. 8 (b), we visualize normalized \tilde{K}_d^{PAR} distributions across months of the year. Normalization was done in the log-scale with the respective station-mean value, which itself was based on monthly mean values across all the years from 2018–2023. We included stations ($n = 55$) where all months from March to October were covered with K_d^{PAR} values from both methods, and where there were at least 36 *in situ* and 100 S3OL2-based estimates, respectively. The temporal distribution shows an overall agreement with higher K_d^{PAR} values in early spring and late summer/autumn, while the period from April to July is characterized by lower values. In March and June, distributions between the *in situ* and S3OL2-based datasets deviate a bit, where K_d^{PAR} seems overestimated by the S3OL2-based model in March and in contrast underestimated in June. From July to October both datasets show parallel increasing trends.

Fig. 6. Deviation analysis between day-precise matchups of both S3OL2 and *in situ* based K_d^{PAR} estimations. Deviations are shown as boxplots of absolute differences on the log-scale for (a) monthly classification and (b) classification by optical depth. Classes overlaid by the orange boxes were excluded from the further analysis.

A huge advantage of satellite-based monitoring is the high spatial coverage that goes far beyond what is possible with *in situ* point samples. In Fig. 9, we present a map of S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} for the whole study area. The map shows K_d^{PAR} calculated based on median values of the three IOPs derived from S3OL2 C2RCC. This map is just one specific example, and in principle it is possible with our method to derive daily maps of K_d^{PAR} , which then can be further processed and aggregated. Blank areas in the map represent pixels where either there were <100 S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} estimates, or the optical depth based on median K_d^{PAR} was <1.5 and consequently excluded due to high uncertainty (Fig. 6). The map shows spatial patterns of S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} with especially high values close to and along the Danish west coast. It is also obvious that there is a clear gradient toward higher K_d^{PAR} values from the open North Sea (a) through Skagerrak (c), Kattegat (d), the belt sea (e-g), and into the Arkona Basin (i) (see Fig. 1 for place names). Further, the Map shows *in situ* monitoring stations with different qualities of coverage from both methods. There are 55 green points, which have good coverage from both datasets and represent those described and considered for the temporal pattern analysis in Fig. 8. The blue points, on the other hand, show where coverage with *in situ*-based K_d^{PAR} values is limited and where S3OL2-based estimates particularly can contribute added value. Red points show optically shallow locations, where there cannot be determined meaningful K_d^{PAR} values based on the new spectral model approach.

For all the points highlighted with numbers in Fig. 9, we prepared detailed Figure collections depicting the spectral model approach for one specific date with matchup at this station, and embedding it in a spatial and temporal context (see Fig. 10 and Figs. S4-S14). In the matchup example shown in Fig. 10, there is good agreement between the estimated K_d^{PAR} from both methods as to be seen in (e) and (f). Further, the overall pattern, and value range from both time-series agree very well (f). K_d^{PAR} is the final product of the developed spectral modelling approach. However, there are intermediate products that might prove useful for many other applications, as there are calculated detailed spectral light compositions (c) and PAR PFDs (d) across different depths of the water column.

4. Discussion

K_d^{PAR} is an important supporting parameter to assess the ecological status in terms of monitoring of eutrophication under the WFD (Christensen et al., 2024; Pawar et al., 2025), as it responds significantly to land derived nutrient loadings and has strong implications for the underwater light availability. It is also a useful proxy for the light dependent depth boundary of submerged aquatic plants such as eelgrass (Nielsen et al., 2002a; Saulquin et al., 2013) and macroalgae (Markager and Sand-Jensen, 1992; Saulquin et al., 2013). It is therefore important that new technologies and approaches used to determine K_d^{PAR} provide robust and accurate estimates if these are to be considered as alternatives or supplements to the traditional ship-based measurements.

In this study we combined S3OL2 C2RCC products with empirical spectral models of IOPs, to determine spectrally resolved estimates of K_d^i and finally K_d^{PAR} . To assess the S3OL2 derived K_d^{PAR} estimates, we compared results with a comprehensive *in situ*-based data set of K_d^{PAR} obtained across the entire Danish seas during 2018 to 2023 and showed the performance added significant value, but also boundaries of applicability of the new method in complex case 2 waters.

Challenges in the retrieval of water quality parameters from S3OL2 C2RCC products in complex coastal areas, as highlighted earlier (Staehr et al., 2022; Masoud, 2022; Staehr et al., 2023), have been minimized by the successful implementation of a multivariate outlier removal routine (Section 2.5.3).

4.1. Comparing apples and pears?

Our results demonstrate that the spectral approach significantly outperforms two simpler empirical approaches (BAC K_d^{490} and AAC K_d^{443}), which apparently estimate other quantities than K_d^{PAR} . This study aimed to move beyond an obvious and widely explored and applied comparison between apples and pears and instead develop a more meaningful comparison — two apples, namely estimates of the same quantity: K_d^{PAR} . But did we succeed?

Our approach successfully estimated the same parameter K_d^{PAR} from S3OL2 C2RCC products, and comparison with *in situ* (ship-based) data yielded an almost perfect linear regression function closely resembling the 1:1 line in Fig. 7 (c). Previous studies have evaluated spatial and temporal patterns in K_d^{PAR} in Danish waters using ship-based estimates (Lund-Hansen, 2004; Lund-Hansen, 2024). Our study is the first to explore these similar patterns using a spectral satellite-based approach (Fig. 8; suppl. Figs. S4-S14). When comparing ship- and satellite-based estimates of K_d^{PAR} it is important to consider that the estimates are derived using two very different methods: While the *in situ* method makes use of light transmission through the water column (Markager and Fossing, 2014), the satellite-based method uses light reflectance from the water column (Doerffer, 2010; Saulquin et al., 2013; Brockmann et al., 2016) — two opposite principles. Furthermore, while the uppermost part of the water column is most crucial for the reflectance signal, this part is mainly neglected from *in situ* assessments due to wave effects and other practical challenges (Markager and Fossing, 2014). As a result, inhomogeneities in the surface of the water column could cause large deviations between K_d^{PAR} estimates from both sources. Furthermore, the underlying IOPs are variable due to a range of physical, chemical and biological conditions. In this study we applied empirical models to describe spectral pigment absorption (Stæhr and Markager, 2004), local spectral CDOM absorption (Stedmon et al., 2000), and the relationship between CDOM and detritus absorption at 443 nm. The applied empirical models are very simple and can obviously only account for parts of the resulting IOP variability. Some of the most important sources of variation in IOPs which may affect our S3OL2-based modelling of K_d^{PAR} are:

- phytoplankton pigment content, composition, and packaging (Bricaud et al., 2004; Stæhr et al., 2004),
- CDOM and detritus content, sources, and quality (Stedmon et al., 2000),
- suspended particle composition and size distribution (Ulloa et al., 1994) influenced by factors such as resuspension events and phytoplankton skeleton.

Not surprisingly, we found deviations between the two methods, including a systematic seasonal pattern with S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} being higher in March, and lower than K_d^{PAR} based on *in situ* PAR-profiles in June (Fig. 8 (b)).

In the eutrophic and phytoplankton rich Danish coastal waters, particularly chlorophyll-*a* (Chl*a*) contributes a lot to the seasonality in light attenuation (Nielsen et al., 2002b). During periods with a strong pycnocline, phytoplankton and hence Chl*a* is not evenly distributed throughout the water column (Lyngsgaard et al., 2014). To investigate the possible influence of vertical gradients in Chl*a*, we obtained Chl*a* depth-profiles from the Danish NOVANA program. Using data for the 55 stations for which temporal patterns were analyzed more closely (Figs. 8 and 9), our analysis showed clear seasonal trends in the ratio between Chl*a* concentration in the uppermost meter Chl*a*₍₀₋₁₎ compared to the upper 10 m of water column Chl*a*₍₀₋₁₀₎ (suppl. Fig. S15). The median ratio Chl*a*₍₀₋₁₎: Chl*a*₍₀₋₁₀₎ was above 1 (accumulation of Chl*a* near the very surface) during January and decreased steadily toward its minimum below 1 (deep Chl*a* maximum) in June. Due to the different nature

Fig. 7. Matchup analysis between K_d^{PAR} estimated through NOVA NA and three S3OL2-based models. Points with optical depth < 1.5 and from November to February (red dots – also see Fig. 6) were excluded from the linear regression and correlation analysis. Further, for (b) and (c) also multivariate outliers (see Fig. 5) were excluded. In (c), comparison to the 1:1 line is also shown, as the S3OL2 model is meant to estimate the same parameter as measured *in situ* in the NOVA NA program. The fitted linear regression model (shown with $p = 0.95$ confidence interval) is very close to the 1:1 line and both slope and intercept (Intcp) are not significantly different from 1 and 0, respectively ($p = 0.05$).

Fig. 8. Spatial and temporal patterns of K_d^{PAR} . (a) K_d^{PAR} distributions across increasing classes of Integrated Bathymetric Proximity (IBP) from both *in situ* monitoring and the spectral model based on S3OL2. Boxplots include all points from each dataset (not only day-precise matchups) and box widths represent the relative number of values represented. IBP is a measure for the minimum spatially integrated sum of bathymetric values from oceanic points to the coast. (b) Station-mean normalized K_d^{PAR} distributions across months of a year from both *in situ* monitoring and the spectral model based on S3OL2. Boxplots include 55 stations with valid coverage for all months from March till October and ≥ 36 *in situ* monitoring and ≥ 100 S3OL2-based K_d^{PAR} estimates over the years 2018–2023. Remark: Boxplots are drawn without outlying points.

of data collection, Chl_a accumulation near the surface will be stronger mirrored in reflectance-based S3OL2 products, while deep Chl_a maxima will have stronger influence on *in situ* PAR profiles and corresponding K_d^{PAR} estimates. Seasonal patterns in Chl_a stratification may therefore partly explain the seasonal deviation between S3OL2 and *in situ* derived K_d^{PAR} .

The spring bloom in Danish waters (suppl. Fig. S15) is typically dominated by diatoms (Carstensen et al., 2015), which exhibit strong pigment packaging (Bricaud and Stramski, 1990) and contain the accessory pigment fucoxanthin, shifting the spectral shape of absorption relative to other phytoplankton groups (Bricaud et al., 2004). C2RCC may not fully account for these spectral characteristics, contributing to discrepancies in S3OL2 vs. *in situ* derived K_d^{PAR} . Due to their silica armor, diatoms contribute significantly to b_{tot}^{443} , but much of this is forward scattering, which minimally affects light attenuation (Ulloa et al., 1994). By assuming a constant backscatter ratio of 0.01 (Section 2.5.5.3), we

may artificially inflate light attenuation estimates under diatom dominance. This suggests that diatom-dominated waters pose a challenge for our spectral approach and may contribute to the deviation between S3OL2 and *in situ* derived K_d^{PAR} observed in spring.

This study brings us closer to an appropriate satellite-based estimation of K_d^{PAR} , while also emphasizing the need to refine IOP-based algorithms to account for more specific optical properties when estimating light attenuation in complex coastal waters. However, do we have suitable means to validate even more complex advanced approaches with *in situ* data for ground truthing? We have discussed here that we in the best case are comparing two different varieties of apples when aligning K_d^{PAR} estimated from both S3OL2 and *in situ* PAR-profiles. We found that refining our model even more for spectral irradiance did not lead to a statistically stronger agreement with the available *in situ* dataset (Section 2.5.7). The same was true for trials with temporally dynamic solar zenith angles (data not shown here). Hence, we argue that

Fig. 9. Map of the median diffuse light attenuation coefficient (K_d^{PAR}) estimated from S3OL2 data for the years 2018–2023. The map is overlaid by points of corresponding *in situ* monitoring stations for K_d^{PAR} (NOVANA), as well as a color code for the coverage of these points by both methods. Red points indicate no coverage by valid S3OL2 data, green points indicate >36 *in situ* and >100 S3OL2 measurements, as well as March till October covered between 2018 and 2023. Blue points indicate >100 S3OL2 measurements, but ≤ 36 *in situ* measurements. Numbers to right of points indicate, there is prepared a detailed Figure collection available depicting the spectral model approach at specific matchup examples and embedding it in a spatial and temporal context. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the online version of this chapter.)

we have now reached a limit for optimization with ground truthing datasets based on *in situ* PAR profiles. For future studies and more refined models of satellite-derived K_d^{PAR} , we recommend the use of spectrally resolved underwater light profile data, which are becoming increasingly available through the globally expanding application of ARGO Floats (Argo) or similar instruments. Recent advancements in radiometry on Argo floats have enabled the measurement of optical and biogeochemical quantities down to a depth of 2000 m, providing valuable data for bio-optical modelling and ocean color remote sensing (Organelli et al., 2017; Jemai et al., 2021).

4.2. Applicability and added value of the satellite-based spectral approach

4.2.1. Potential for spatial generalization

The spectral approach developed to estimate K_d^{PAR} from S3OL2 IOP data involved several steps, including use of simple empirical models (Fig. 2). However, only two assumptions were justified based on regional data and references: (1) The constant distribution ratio between CDOM and detritus absorption coefficients at 443 nm $a_g^{443}/a_d^{443} = 0.7/0.3$ (Section 2.5.5.2), as well as (2) the backscatter ratio of 0.01 (Section 2.5.5.3). A strength in our analysis is that it involved all Danish marine waters, thus covering a highly diverse and optically complex system from the high saline open North Sea all the way into the brackish Baltic Sea. Therefore, we assume that our approach should be of relevance for many other marine systems worldwide and for other satellite sensors compatible with the C2RCC processor. It would therefore be very interesting to test our modelling approach in other systems where high quality *in situ* K_d^{PAR} data are available.

4.2.2. Limitations with K_d^{PAR} as environmental indicator and advantages of spectral approaches

PAR measures the total photon flux available between 400 and 700 nm, without distinguishing between wavelengths. This poses limitations when assessing underwater light availability for primary production of either phytoplankton or submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV). These

primarily rely on blue (~ 445 nm) and red (~ 660 nm) wavelengths for photosynthesis, representing the absorption peaks for Chla (Markager and Vincent, 2001).

As we have shown in this study for the complex case 2 waters around Denmark, green (~ 500 – 550 nm) light penetrates the deepest (Fig. 10, suppl. Figs. S4–S14), while blue and red light is in general absorbed rapidly on its way through the water column, especially the red photons that get absorbed rapidly on the top layers (Saulquin et al., 2013). However, green light is not as efficiently used for photosynthesis. This can lead to overestimation of the actual photosynthetically useful light available, when using PAR and K_d^{PAR} . K_d^i and spectral downwelling irradiance are intermediate products of our approach and could in future studies be tested for potentially more accurate assessments of phytoplankton primary production and habitat suitability for SAV, like the “matching parameter for algal photosynthesis under different spectral regimes” developed by Markager and Vincent (2001).

5. Conclusions and perspectives

The findings of our study show that we can successfully apply S3OL2 data to estimate valid K_d^{PAR} values for complex and near-coastal marine areas. Given the high frequency and large coverage of S3OL2 data, this enables us to considerably increase the currently limited spatial and temporal coverage with K_d^{PAR} monitoring sites by supplementing data from national monitoring programs with satellite-derived products as a value-adding complement. Valuable information on currently unmonitored areas would enhance the representativity of aggregated values, as for example annual averages across spatially outlined water bodies. This is of particular importance for environmental status assessments, as they are required in the frame of the EU Water Framework Directive, or Marine Strategy Framework Directive. Moreover, the new data would enhance our ability to describe and understand spatially and temporally continuous processes leading to the observed dynamics in K_d^{PAR} and underwater light availability for marine ecosystems. For example, the partial contributions of several optically active components to overall

Fig. 10. Detailed Figure collection for point 6 in Fig. 9, depicting the spectral model approach for a matchup on 2023-03-01, and embedding it in a spatial and temporal context. (a) Map with the highlighted location of the station; (b) result of the spectral IOP model approach (see Section 2.5.5) and derived spectral K_d^λ (see Section 2.5.6); (c) propagation of a constant photon flux density from 400 to 700 nm through the water column and the resulting change in spectral light composition; (d) alignment of the estimation of K_d^{PAR} from both *in situ* (green) and S3OL2 (blue) by fitting linear models through $\log(\text{PAR})$ depth-profiles, (e) matchup points of the respective station (orange) and the specific matchup from 2023 to 03-01 (red) in the context of all 1458 daily matchup points used in this study; (f) time-series for the specific station with both *in situ* (green) and S3OL2 (blue) based K_d^{PAR} estimates. Matchup pairs are enlarged, and the specific pair on 2023-01-01 is highlighted in red. The blue line represents a ± 15 -days moving average for the S3OL2-based dataset. Corresponding Figure collections for points 2–11 in Fig. 9 can be found in suppl. Figs. S4–S14. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the online version of this chapter.)

K_d^{PAR} , similar to the approach by Lund-Hansen (2024), could be analyzed continuously along spatial and environmental gradients to understand cumulative effects of different sources of optically active components. Hence, we recommend allocating future efforts into operationalization

of the approach on a daily basis. Although this study is based on Danish marine waters, we consider the developed method from this study spatially generalizable to major parts of the global marine waters with only minor adjustments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andreas Holbach: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sanjina Upadhyay Stæhr:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Peter Anton Upadhyay Stæhr:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Stiig Markager:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to make the abstract fit with the journal's requirements. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was partly funded by (1) the 'Danish Agency for Green Transition and Aquatic Environment', (former Danish Environmental Protection Agency) in the frame of the IMM (Integrated Marine environmental Monitoring) project, and the (2) OBAMA-NEXT (observing and mapping marine ecosystems — next generation tools) project, which is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (grant agreement no. 101081642).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.179775>.

Data availability

All data used in the study are publicly available

References

- Bricaud, A., Stramski, D., 1990. Spectral absorption coefficients of living phytoplankton and nonalgal biogenous matter: a comparison between the Peru upwelling area and the Sargasso Sea. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 35, 562–582.
- Bricaud, A., Claustre, H., Ras, J., Oubelkheir, K., 2004. Natural variability of phytoplanktonic absorption in oceanic waters: influence of the size structure of algal populations. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* 109.
- Brockmann, C., Doerffer, R., Peters, M., Kerstin, S., Embacher, S., Ruescas, A., 2016. Evolution of the C2rc neural network for sentinel 2 and 3 for the retrieval of ocean colour products in normal and extreme optically complex waters. *Living Planet Symposium*. 740, 54.
- Carstensen, J., Klais, R., Cloern, J.E., 2015. Phytoplankton blooms in estuarine and coastal waters: seasonal patterns and key species. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 162, 98–109.
- Christensen, J.P.A., Timmermann, K., Erichsen, A., Larsen, T.C., 2024. Tilvejebringelse af hydromorfologiske og fysisk-kemiske kvalitetselementer for danske kystvande.
- Doerffer, R., 2010. OLCI Level 2: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document—Ocean Colour Turbid Water. Document Ref: S3-L2-SD-03-C11-GKSS-ATBD. Accessed at: <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/user-guides/sentinel-3-olci>.
- EMODnet, 2024. EMODnet Digital Bathymetry (DTM 2022), tiles D4, D5, D6.
- EUMETSAT, 2024. Sentinel-3 Ocean Colour Level 2 Data Guide.
- Geodatastyrelsen, 2024. Danish Geodata Agency — Denmark's Depth Model, 50 m Resolution.
- Gordon, H.R., 1989. Can the Lambert-beer law be applied to the diffuse attenuation coefficient of ocean water? *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 34, 1389–1409.

- Hedley, J., Mobley, C., 2019. HYDROLIGHT 6.0 ECOLIGHT 6.0 Technical Documentation. Numerical Optics Ltd, Tiverton, UK.
- Jemai, A., Wollschläger, J., Voß, D., Zielinski, O., 2021. Radiometry on Argo floats: from the multispectral state-of-the-art on the step to hyperspectral technology. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 676537.
- Jerlov, N.G., 1976. *Marine Optics*. Elsevier.
- Kirk, J., 1977. Attenuation of light in natural waters. *Mar. Freshw. Res.* 28, 497–508.
- Kirk, J., 1984. Dependence of relationship between inherent and apparent optical properties of water on solar altitude. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 29, 350–356.
- Kirk, J.T., 1994. *Light and Photosynthesis in Aquatic Ecosystems*. Cambridge University Press.
- Klimadatasstyrelsen, 2025. Danish Agency for Climate Data. Topografisk Landpolygon.
- Kratzer, S., Allart, M., 2023. Links between land cover and in-water optical properties in four optically contrasting Swedish bays. *Remote Sens. (Basel)* 16, 176.
- Kratzer, S., Kyriliuk, D., Edman, M., Philipson, P., Lyon, S.W., 2019. Synergy of satellite, in situ and modelled data for addressing the scarcity of water quality information for eutrophication assessment and monitoring of Swedish coastal waters. *Remote Sens. (Basel)* 11, 2051.
- Lee, Z.P., Du, K.P., Arnone, R., 2005. A model for the diffuse attenuation coefficient of downwelling irradiance. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* 110.
- Lee, Z., Shang, S., Du, K., Wei, J., 2018. Resolving the long-standing puzzles about the observed Secchi depth relationships. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 63, 2321–2336.
- Loisel, H., Vantrepotte, V., Dessailly, D., Mériaux, X., 2014. Assessment of the colored dissolved organic matter in coastal waters from ocean color remote sensing. *Opt. Express* 22, 13109–13124.
- Luis, K.M., Rheuban, J.E., Kavanaugh, M.T., Glover, D.M., Wei, J., Lee, Z., et al., 2019. Capturing coastal water clarity variability with Landsat 8. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 145, 96–104.
- Lund-Hansen, L.C., 2004. Diffuse attenuation coefficients K_d (PAR) at the estuarine North Sea–Baltic Sea transition: time-series, partitioning, absorption, and scattering. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 61, 251–259.
- Lund-Hansen, L.C., 2024. A 30-year (1992–2021) time-series of K_d (PAR) at the North Sea–Baltic Sea transitional zone-trends in light attenuation and chlorophyll a. *Reg. Stud. Mar. Sci.* 70, 103367.
- Lyngsgaard, M.M., Markager, S., Richardson, K., 2014. Changes in the vertical distribution of primary production in response to land-based nitrogen loading. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 59, 1679–1690.
- Markager, S., Fossing, H., 2014. Lyssvækkelse. Teknisk anvisning M06, v.3.
- Markager, S., Sand-Jensen, K., 1992. Light requirements and depth zonation of marine macroalgae. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 88, 83–92.
- Markager, S., Vincent, W.F., 2001. Light absorption by phytoplankton: development of a matching parameter for algal photosynthesis under different spectral regimes. *J. Plankton Res.* 23, 1373–1384.
- Masoud, A.A., 2022. On the retrieval of the water quality parameters from sentinel-3/2 and landsat-8 OLI in the Nile delta's coastal and inland waters. *Water* 14, 593.
- Mobley, C.D., 1994. *Light and Water: Radiative Transfer in Natural Waters* (No Title).
- Mobley, C.D., Stramski, D., Bissett, P., Paul W., Boss, E., 2004. Optical modeling of ocean waters: is the case 1-case 2 classification still useful? *Oceanography* 17, 60.
- Morel, A., Antoine, D., 1994. Heating rate within the upper ocean in relation to its bio-optical state. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* 24, 1652–1665.
- Nielsen, S.L., Sand-Jensen, K., Borum, J., Geertz-Hansen, O., 2002a. Depth colonization of eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) and macroalgae as determined by water transparency in Danish coastal waters. *Estuaries* 25, 1025–1032.
- Nielsen, S.L., Sand-Jensen, K., Borum, J., Geertz-Hansen, O., 2002b. Phytoplankton, nutrients, and transparency in Danish coastal waters. *Estuaries* 25, 930–937.
- Obrador, B., Pretus, J.L., 2008. Light regime and components of turbidity in a Mediterranean coastal lagoon. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 77, 123–133.
- Organelli, E., Barbieux, M., Claustre, H., Schmechtig, C., Poteau, A., Bricaud, A., et al., 2017. Two databases derived from BGC-Argo float measurements for marine biogeochemical and bio-optical applications. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 9, 861–880.
- Pawar, S., Gonçalves-Araujo, R., Timmermann, K., 2025. In search of light: estimating diffuse attenuation coefficient of downwelling irradiance and its variation in optically complex shallow water habitats using Sentinel-2 imagery. *Sci. Total Environ.* 965, 178598.
- Platt, T., Sathyendranath, S., Caverhill, C.M., Lewis, M.R., 1988. Ocean primary production and available light: further algorithms for remote sensing. *Deep Sea Res. Part A. Oceanogr. Res. Papers* 35, 855–879.
- Sathyendranath, S., Platt, T., Caverhill, C.M., Warnock, R.E., Lewis, M.R., 1989. Remote sensing of oceanic primary production: computations using a spectral model. *Deep Sea Res. Part A. Oceanogr. Res. Papers* 36, 431–453.
- Saulquin, B., Hamdi, A., Gohin, F., Populus, J., Mangin, A., d'Andon, O.F., 2013. Estimation of the diffuse attenuation coefficient K_dPAR using MERIS and application to seabed habitat mapping. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 128, 224–233.
- Stæhr, P., Markager, S., 2004. Parameterization of the chlorophyll a-specific in vivo light absorption coefficient covering estuarine, coastal and oceanic waters. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 25, 5117–5130.
- Stæhr, P., Markager, S., Sand-Jensen, K., 2004. Pigment specific in vivo light absorption of marine phytoplankton from different trophic regimes. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 275, 115–128.
- Stæhr, S.U., Van der Zande, D., Stæhr, P.A., Markager, S., 2022. Suitability of multisensory satellites for long-term chlorophyll assessment in coastal waters: a case study in optically-complex waters of the temperate region. *Ecol. Indic.* 134, 108479.
- Stæhr, S.U., Holbach, A.M., Markager, S., Stæhr, P.A.U., 2023. Exploratory study of the Sentinel-3 level 2 product for monitoring chlorophyll-a and assessing ecological status in Danish seas. *Sci. Total Environ.* 897, 165310.

- Stedmon, C.A., Markager, S., Kaas, H., 2000. Optical properties and signatures of chromophoric dissolved organic matter (CDOM) in Danish coastal waters. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 51, 267–278.
- Ulloa, O., Sathyendranath, S., Platt, T., 1994. Effect of the particle-size distribution on the backscattering ratio in seawater. *Appl. Optics* 33, 7070–7077.
- Wetzel, R.G., 2001. *Limnology: Lake and River Ecosystems*. Gulf Professional Publishing.
- Woźniak, S.B., Sagan, S., Zabłocka, M., Stoń-Egiert, J., Borzycka, K., 2018. Light scattering and backscattering by particles suspended in the Baltic Sea in relation to the mass concentration of particles and the proportions of their organic and inorganic fractions. *J. Mar. Syst.* 182, 79–96.
- Zaneveld, J.R.V., Kitchen, J.C., Pak, H., 1981. The influence of optical water type on the heating rate of a constant depth mixed layer. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* 86 (C7), 6426–6428.
- Zhang, M., Tang, J., Song, Q., Dong, Q., 2010. Backscattering ratio variation and its implications for studying particle composition: a case study in yellow and East China seas. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* 115.